

SHARING ELECTRICITY DISTRIBUTION DATA VIA ENERGY DATA SPACES WITH DATAMITE

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Abstract

Data management and sharing plays a crucial role in the new energy matrix, mainly to DSOs, since network data is needed, for instance, by energy stakeholders to take part in new opportunities in the energy system, which can be done via open data sharing, and by Energy Service Providers to develop system planning tools for DSOs. The Energy Data Spaces are being developed to facilitate data sharing between these stakeholders. DATAMITE, which is an open-source modular and multi-domain framework that focuses on monetisation through interoperability and data exchange, incorporates the appropriate connectors for data sharing to a collection of ecosystems, including Energy Data Spaces, through a plugin-based approach. This paper delves on how electricity distribution data can be shared by DSOs through Energy Data Spaces via the DATAMITE Framework by explaining the use cases implemented by E-REDES, in Portugal, to leverage its open data portal and to test sharing data products to external stakeholders, and by HEDNO, in Greece, to allow data exchange between a DSO and an energy service provider for system planning enhancement. By enhancing data sharing, DATAMITE can leverage several use cases such as the provision of metering data to consumers, contributing to a sustainable energy ecosystem.

1 Introduction

The number of IT/OT devices connected in the energy system is increasing. With this, the number of data points and the volume of data being collected, treated and shared by the energy stakeholders is also increasing. For instance, E-REDES, the Portuguese main electricity Distribution System Operator (DSO) has to deal with more than 400 million of data records every day, with a 3 Terabyte (TB) volume. The energy system is also becoming more integrated, with a cross-sector approach, which demands a close collaboration between all the stakeholders involved in the system management and operation, where data management and sharing plays a crucial role.

The process of sharing data involves data collection, handling, and validation, to ensure proper data availability, access and quality. This requires a range of capabilities, including data discovery and governance, harmonisation of data formats, and the addition of semantic layers to reduce system frictions and

enhance interoperability. It also involves ensuring that sensitive data is handled in compliance with regulatory requirements, such as anonymisation procedures, and defining and enforcing data access and usage policies.

Data sharing plays an important role in several critical tasks, either for external stakeholders in the energy matrix or internally for DSOs. On one hand, the actors in the energy matrix seek access to various types of network data, for instance, to optimise energy usage and generation profiles, facilitate renewable energy integration, and provide flexibility to the grid. On the other hand, the DSO provides data to energy service providers, who use advanced tools for system planning, aiming to optimise decision support and investments by taking into consideration the projected penetration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and stochastic loads. One way to provide this information is through open data sharing. Various DSOs have their own dedicated open data platforms, such as ORES, Stedin, Fluvius, ENEDIS, and E-REDES [1]. However, open data sharing is a costly and decentralised

process that requires a standardised method to prepare data as open data products and share these products with external stakeholders. Alternatively, some DSOs, such as HEDNO, provide similar data upon request through offline procedures.

The lack of automation in data preparation and sharing, combined with the lack of efficient mechanism to apply sufficient quality criteria to the data, not only hampers data sharing but also limits opportunities for monetisation and collaboration. There are solutions for data governance, quality or security, both proprietary [2] [3] [4] [5] or open source [6] [7] [8]. These solutions mostly focus on the in-company management of data, offering governance and quality functionalities [4] [8], but none of these include data sharing capabilities. OpenMetadata [8] considers data sharing but lacks the integration of the appropriate connectors.

The role of data in the new energy matrix is recognised by the energy players, with a specific focus on data sharing within the various stakeholders [9]. The European Commission (EC) also recognised the importance of data sharing by stating the necessity of having a dedicated infrastructure to enhance data sharing between the stakeholders, which will be made possible through the development of the Common European Energy Data Space (CEEDS) [10].

Data spaces facilitate secure data sharing among multiple participants by providing both organisational agreements and the necessary technical infrastructure. A key design principle of data spaces is to maintain data sovereignty for all participants, allowing even the most sensitive and valuable data to be shared with trusted partners. Within a data space, data providers can be confident that their partners will manage the data responsibly and that they will receive value in return. Meanwhile, data consumers can trust that the data they use comes from a reliable source. A data space high-level architecture can be observed in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 IDS Data Spaces functional architecture

As a non-profit organisation with more than 160 members, the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) [11] [12] establishes standards for data spaces and offers resources for designing, implementing and governing data spaces such as the IDSA Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM) [13], the IDS Rulebook [14] describing how to implement and operationalise data spaces, IDS certification scheme [15] and the Dataspace protocol [16] for ensuring interoperability.

In the energy sector, the IDSA Energy Interoperability Task Force with experts from OMEGA-X, ENERSHARE, DATA CELLAR, EDDIE, SYNERGIES projects, and their associated Coordination and Support Action (CSA, Int:net) plays an important role in promoting cross-data space interoperability within the energy sector. While the task force's primary focus lies in achieving technical and semantic interoperability, it also addresses organisational and legal interoperability to ensure a holistic approach. In [17], the task force outlines strategies to tackle these challenges, leveraging existing reference architectures like the Common Information Model (CIM) and the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM), while proposing enhancements for energy-specific applications. The framework emphasises interoperable data formats, exchange protocols, and identity management systems, coupled with standardised legal and organisational practices, to facilitate secure and efficient collaboration.

DATAMITE [18] is an open-source modular and multi-domain framework that focuses on monetisation through interoperability and data exchange. Its modules offer tools for enhancing data governance, quality and security, but also incorporates the appropriate connectors for data sharing to a collection of ecosystems, including Energy Data Spaces, through a plugin-based approach. It also includes support tools to assist on data discovery, ingestion, harmonisation or evaluate data fairness.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses the integration process of DATAMITE, outlining the framework's architecture while addressing key aspects such as its integration into energy data spaces, data preparation, governance, and sovereignty. Section 3 examines the data sharing use cases employed by E-REDES and HEDNO. Finally, Section 4 concludes by highlighting the benefits of DATAMITE for DSOs, emphasising its transformative impact on the sector.

2. Methodology

Fig. 2 depicts the DATAMITE architecture and its different components. DATAMITE allows data ingestion of bulk data and uses a plugin-based approach to ingest streaming data from different technologies or discover data from databases and repositories. During these processes, all the available information about the data is captured as metadata (e.g., description, owner, creation date, etc.) and the data itself is profiled with the Data Quality module. DATAMITE includes a KPI library with a broad number of inherent/informative KPIs (e.g., statistics), but also allows users to define their own business quality rules, that can be also used in the profile. The metadata resulting from ingestion and profiling is pushed to the governance module and made available in the catalogue. Users can then enrich these data with descriptions or linking it with terms from business vocabularies that have been previously defined in the data glossary.

Once catalogued datasets have been enriched, it can be combined, aggregated or used to compose data products, whose quality is reassessed if needed. Data products can be extended, optionally, with data usage or access control policies, defined with the data sovereignty component using standards like ODRL [19]. DATAMITE includes a set of supplementary support tools that provide functionalities like AI-assisted anonymisation, harmonisation, or detection and mitigation of biases ensuring fairness, that can be used to further enhance or tune data products. Once ready, data products can be shared via an Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) [20] connector to data spaces or Gaia-X or, alternatively, via purposely defined plugins to different EU Portals, Marketplaces, Open-Data portals or initiatives such as the AI-on-Demand [21] platform. Furthermore, the data-sharing logging tool monitors actions performed during the preparation and sharing of data products, thereby improving the platform's auditability and transparency. Note also that access control mechanisms assure fine-grained access to data products, thereby maintaining security and compliance with data governance policies.

DATAMITE provides Gaia-X data product onboarding and Credential Event Service (CES) [22] publishing functionalities to facilitate the on-boarding and data products publishing in a Gaia-X compliant data space. This assists on the creation of a decentralised identity, following the Gaia-X compliance processes, both for the company and the offered data products, and publishing the data products using the Gaia-X CES functionality.

Finally, the data sharing phase assures that the data sovereignty rules are respected during the data exchange. The so-called participant agent provides the technical infrastructure to support the data product consumption, including the negotiation process, the data transfer, the data access/usage policies enforcement, and monitoring facilities among others. DATAMITE uses the EDC connector as the base for the participant agent, adding two extensions: the policy engine to enforce data usage policies and the logging service extension to send information about the data product usage life cycle to an external logger that provides tracking and auditing functionalities for the data space.

The DATAMITE architecture is being tested in 6 pilots, divided into 3 use cases. One of the use cases is focused on the energy sector data sharing and is being tested by E-REDES, in Portugal, and by HEDNO, in Greece.

Fig. 2 DATAMITE High Level Architecture

2.1 Leveraging Gaia-X and data spaces

A generic data provider journey is outlined below, focusing on how challenges like data value, interoperability, and sovereignty are addressed at each stage, along with the modules that support this process in a data space context.

The main phases needed to participate in a data space are on-boarding, metadata publishing/finding and data sharing/monitoring. The on-boarding phase comprises the steps needed to become a participant according to the rules, policies, models defined by the data space authority. This is paramount to generate trust, since all participants must adhere to the same rules and provide trusted information about themselves and their data products, using a common format.

The data publishing phase makes the data product information and metadata available to the data space so that any other participant can find data products, evaluate, and eventually use them. Including data quality, data access/usage policies, and business information along with the semantic description of the data included in the data product, allows the possible consumers to evaluate the adequacy of the data product to specific use case needs.

3. Results

3.1 Leverage electricity distribution open data

E-REDES offers an open data solution where any interested stakeholder can access 25 different types of datasets related to energy consumption, electric mobility, electrical networks, quality of service and renewables [1]. The DATAMITE framework is being integrated and tested in E-REDES to leverage the open data portal, enhance its capabilities, and to test data sharing to external stakeholders through the CEEDS.

The framework is being deployed in E-REDES premises, on a Microsoft Azure based environment, which is composed by a Virtual Machine (VM) that hosts the DATAMITE components running in containerised instances using Docker, an Azure Data Lake Storage (ADLS) Gen 2 that serves as a storage solution for the datasets, and a Databricks service that allows the connection to the ADLS and the VM, allowing to access the datasets, making changes to them, and connecting to the DATAMITE components. The pilot is being tested in three levels, as it can be observed in Fig. 3 a.

In the 1st level, the aggregated open datasets together with some of their artifacts are moved from the internal ADLS, managed by the E-REDES BI team, to the project's dedicated ADLS to make them available to the project tools and connectors. In the 2nd level, the datasets will be evaluated through the quality evaluator tool, which considers several quality rules defined by E-REDES. These rules fall mainly on

the Completeness, and Accuracy Data Quality (DQ) dimensions, such as null checks and coherence with real world concepts (e.g. the rated power of a lamp can't be less than or equal to zero), respectively [23]. This step is crucial to ensure that data has enough quality to be shared with third parties. All the information related to the dataset will be described and stored in the metadata repository, together with the results from the quality evaluation. This information is made available through the glossaries, vocabularies and dictionaries developed in the project. These steps are necessary for the creation of data products, which is the 1st step of the 3rd level of the demonstration. These products are created when requested by the data consumer and will be shared through the open data portal and the CEEDS using the EDC connector, while complying with the IDSA and Gaia-X frameworks, allowing to keep data on premises for on-demand requests, while defining relevant rules for data access from the Data Consumer, through the Data Security Module. These data products are expected to be shared through the OMEGA-X [24] and the DATA CELLAR [25] Energy Data Spaces, which will broaden the dissemination of the open data products to external stakeholders.

files are stored in an S3-compatible object storage service. Additionally, data will also be manually uploaded to DATAMITE, either in CSV format (for SCADA and AMI) or in PowerFactory format. The framework is being deployed within HEDNO's IT infrastructure, using a two-VM setup with access to the databases and the storage service.

HEDNO's initial goal is to achieve and demonstrate the seamless integration of the DATAMITE framework with all three data sources, utilising the built-in connectors of the Data Discovery Tools. Next, the focus shifts to the Data Quality and Data Governance modules. Specifically, with the Data Quality module, HEDNO will define and apply user-defined quality rules, with the predefined KPIs, to evaluate the data and ensure it meets the necessary quality criteria before being shared with third parties. Meanwhile, the Data Governance module will track the history and changes of the datasets and provide all metadata to the data catalogue. Subsequently, HEDNO plans to demonstrate creating data products, assigning and enforcing access/usage policies to them, and sharing them to an energy service provider. A composite data product will be created using data from all three energy sources, after anonymising any sensitive user information, so that it can be used for simulations. The exchange of the data product will take place through an Energy Data Space aligned with the initiatives of IDSA and Gaia-X, and potentially DATA CELLAR. This process will utilise the EDC connector, which also enforces the access/usage policies. CERTH will then consume the data products, run system planning simulations and provide feedback with the results to HEDNO. A depiction of the data exchange scenario is shown in Fig. 3 b.

Fig. 3 Overview of data exchange scenarios of (a) E-REDES, and (b) HEDNO-CERTH, using DATAMITE.

3.2 Data exchange between a Distribution System Operator and an energy service provider

HEDNO may be assisted by energy service providers for system planning, including the optimal placement and sizing of assets (e.g., RES, voltage regulators, EV chargers, and batteries), reducing energy losses, mitigating congestion, forecasting load demand and distributed energy resource (DER) generation, and estimating system variables.

There are three types of essential datasets for system planning simulations: a) measurements from the SCADA system monitoring medium-voltage lines, b) data collected from medium-voltage customers via the Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), and c) network topology PowerFactory files. For the first two data sources, HEDNO employs dedicated PostgreSQL databases, while the network topology

4 Conclusion

The DATAMITE project offers significant benefits to DSOs and other energy sector players by enabling and facilitating open data sharing through Energy Data Spaces, promoting the adoption of open standards, and fostering collaboration with stakeholders. It supports the creation of new research and innovation projects while empowering DSOs to share data with energy service providers, driving the development of advanced system planning tools, including data-driven and AI-based solutions. Additionally, by enhancing data sharing, DATAMITE can be used to leverage several use cases such as the provision of metering data to consumers, to enable energy-saving initiatives, Demand Response programs, and client-specific grid observability, enhancing transparency, efficiency, and personalised service. Another aspect is that DATAMITE can further support the integration of distributed generation since the standardised access to grid information can be used to optimise the planning and operation of distributed energy assets, contributing to a smarter and more sustainable energy ecosystem.

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